

Research paper

Reversible high-temperature heat pumps for peak load coverage in geothermal heating plants: A techno-economic analysis

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ABSTRACT

High-temperature heat pumps (HTHP) are a promising technology to cover the peak demand in geothermal heating plants (GHP) during winter, but are often not economical due to few operational hours. Reversible HTHPs (RHP), which can also operate as an ORC for power generation, could tackle this issue. Therefore, this work investigates the use of RHPs for peak load coverage in GHPs by means of annual plant simulations. The subsequent techno-economic analysis compares the RHP to conventional peak load technologies such as HTHPs and gas boilers. By introducing a physical model for the air-cooled condenser (ACC), part load effects during ORC operation and the impact of different ACC sizes are investigated. The results show that the ACC size can be reduced by 50% of its initial value without relevant reductions in annual net electricity generation. With a 50% reduced ACC size, the RHP becomes competitive, yielding a levelised cost of heat (LCOH) of 145.4€/MWh, and replaces the HTHP (LCOH of 150.4€/MWh) as the second-best peak load system after the gas boiler (LCOH of 99.9€/MWh) for 2024 energy prices. Finally, a sensitivity analysis is conducted to investigate the impact of fluctuating energy prices, different ACC sizes and varying electricity price ratios (i.e. the ratio of sales and purchase price). The results indicate that RHPs and HTHPs are most competitive for higher gas prices and the RHP system is well suited to lower the investment risk, as it shows a high resilience towards fluctuating electricity prices.

1. Introduction

This section first introduces the general motivation for investigating reversible high-temperature heat pumps in the context of geothermal heat and power plants. Subsequently, a literature review summarises the state-of-the-art for such reversible systems for different applications. Based on this, the last section of this chapter derives the research gaps in the field and defines the respective contribution of the present work.

1.1. Motivation

The omnipresent threat of global warming has led to an unprecedented rise in the global use of renewable energy sources within the last decades. Between 2013 and 2023 alone, the global installed renewable power capacity more than doubled from 1.57 TW to 3.87 TW [1]. Especially efforts in renewable electricity generation have led to significant shares of green electricity for many countries. For instance, Germany was able to cover 51.8% of its gross electricity consumption from renewable sources in the year 2023 [2]. In contrast to this, renewable

heat supply, which has long been treated with less attention, significantly lags behind the renewable electricity shares and only 18.6% of Germany's 2023 gross energy consumption for heating and cooling came from renewable sources [2]. A similar picture can be observed in Europe, where in 2021, the majority of countries covered below 40% of their heating and cooling demand from renewable sources. Especially other high-demand countries like Spain, Italy and France all had renewable heating and cooling shares below 25% in 2021 [3]. This poses a major challenge for politics, industry, private consumers and research alike. In an attempt to decarbonise residential and commercial heating, numerous geothermal heating plants (GHP) have been put into operation in different European countries throughout the last decade, supplying large amounts of heat to local district heating networks (DHN) [4]. The goal to cover large shares of the European heat demand by DHNs [5] imposes an increasing heat demand on existing GHPs, often exceeding the thermal power of the respective geothermal wells. This can already be examined for the south German molasse basin (facilitating multiple geothermal heating projects), where the number of consumers connected to the respective DHNs is seeing a continuous

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Nomenclature**Abbreviations**

ACC	air-cooled condenser
CEPCI	chemical engineering plant cost index
CHP	combined heat and power
COP	coefficient of performance
DHN	district heating network
EF	emission factor
EPC	engineering, procurement and construction
EUA	European emission allowance
GHP	geothermal heating plant
HTHP	high temperature heat pump
LCOH	levelised cost of heat
LMTD	logarithmic mean temperature difference
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
PBP	payback period
PHEX	plate heat exchanger
PTES	pumped thermal electricity storage
RHP	reversible heat pump
RLP	reference load profile
RMSE	root mean square error

Subscripts

1	first year of operation
BP	brine pump
comp	compressor
C	capital-related
D	demand-related
DP	design point
el	electrical/electricity
el-mech	electro-mechanical
exp	expander
hyd	hydraulic
HEX	heat exchangers
<i>i</i>	component iteration index
in	at the pump inlet
inst	installation
I	installation-related
<i>j</i>	time iteration index
loss	with respect to losses
mech	mechanical
M	maintenance-related
M	material-specific
<i>N</i>	with respect to annuity
out	at the pump outlet
O	operation-related
p-t	pipng and tanks
P	pressure-specific
ref	reference
R	revenue-related
s	swept
th	thermal
<i>T</i>	temperature-specific
s+i	servicing and inspection
w	weighted

Latin symbols

<i>a</i>	annuity factor, -
<i>A</i>	annuity, €
<i>A</i>	area, m ²
<i>b</i>	price dynamic chash value factor, -
<i>c</i>	specific cost, €/MWh
<i>C</i>	cost, €
<i>d</i>	diameter, m
<i>e</i>	roughness, m
<i>E</i>	annual electricity generation, J
<i>f</i>	(correction-)factor, -
<i>g</i>	gravitational acceleration, m/s ²
<i>m</i>	mass flow, kg/s
<i>H</i>	height or pressure head, m
<i>n</i>	exponential coefficient, -
<i>n</i>	shaft rotation speed, rpm or Hz
<i>p</i>	pressure, Pa
<i>P</i>	power, W
<i>q</i>	interest factor, -
<i>Q</i>	heat, J
<i>Q̇</i>	heat flow, W
<i>r</i>	price change factor, -
<i>R</i>	revenue, €
<i>t</i>	time, h
<i>T</i>	temperature, K or °C
<i>U</i>	heat transfer coefficient, W/(m ² K)
<i>v</i>	specific volume, m ³ /kg
<i>V</i>	volume, m ³
<i>V̇</i>	volumetric flowrate, m ³ /s
<i>X</i>	cost scaling property
<i>y</i>	cost scaling exponent, -

Greek symbols

η	efficiency, - or %
λ	friction factor, -
ρ	density, kg/m ³
τ	observation period, years

rise [6]. When the geothermal heat supply cannot cover the demand, oil- or gas-fired peak load boilers are commonly operated during winter times to make up for the deficit. A promising technology to also decarbonise the peak load coverage of these plants is the use of a high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) driven by renewable electricity. This technology has gained a lot of attention from academia and industry alike during the last few years and has accordingly matured significantly. During the last years, the respective costs of gas and electricity have made the economic viability of HTHPs economically unattractive or dependent on subsidies in many cases [7]. Moreover, the integration of available HTHPs can be hindered by a low number of operational hours throughout the year, which makes the investment less profitable as discussed by Schlosser et al. [8]. This situation could be improved by the introduction of reversible HTHPs (RHPs), which are also capable of operating as an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) during times of excess heat from the geothermal well. Besides a larger number of annual operating hours, the revenues from the generated electricity could reduce the plant's annuity and thereby the levelised cost of heat (LCOH) for peak load coverage, depending on the additional cost compared to a conventional HTHP.

1.2. Literature review

An RHP facilitates two processes in a single plant, with the first one being a vapour compression heat pump. The temperature requirements for current DHNs oftentimes exceed the capabilities of regular heat pumps and, therefore, require the installation of HTHPs. These plants are characterised by condensation temperatures in the range between 90 °C and 160 °C [9]. As these elevated temperatures come along with numerous challenges regarding the choice of working fluids and suitable plant components, especially compressors, the development of HTHPs has only picked up speed in recent years. This development was accelerated by the urgent requirement for renewable heating solutions, and currently, a significant number of publications investigate HTHPs in experimental or simulative studies. In this context, different applications for HTHPs are described in literature. Several authors highlight the enormous process heat demand in the chemical and food industry, e.g. for steam production or drying processes, where HTHPs could play a key role on the pathway to decarbonisation [9–11]. Other uses include base- or peak-load supply to DHNs [7,12] or the application in pumped thermal electricity storage (PTES) systems [13]. A significant number of suppliers already provide commercial HTHP solutions in the heat sink temperature range of 100 °C to 200 °C [14]. Several studies on the economic feasibility of HTHPs have been published in recent years. Ommen et al. [15] performed a techno-economic evaluation for different plant layouts of single-stage industrial heat pumps. They introduce the net present value and the payback period (PBP) as economic performance indicators and use an exponential scaling approach for component cost estimation. Their findings indicate that the economic viability of an HTHP strongly depends on the application's temperature requirements and the applied working fluid. In a similar work, Kosmadakis et al. [16] present the techno-economic evaluation of HTHPs for waste heat recovery using environmentally friendly working fluids of the latest generation. Their cost estimation approach combines methods from previously described literature sources [15,17–19] and a discounted PBP is introduced for economic plant evaluation. The study confirms that a recuperated single-stage HTHP is suitable for most of the evaluated applications and economically viable.

The second process realised in an RHP, the ORC, is well established in commercial plants and has been the subject of research for decades [20]. Despite the comparatively broad knowledge base compared to HTHPs, ORCs are still the subject of research and various aspects such as novel cycle concepts, optimised expansion devices and future-proof working fluids are investigated [21]. Due to the vast number of publications on ORC technology, a detailed review of ORC technology would exceed the scope of this work, and hence, only some relevant studies investigating the techno-economic performance of ORC units are presented subsequently. Braimakis and Karellas [17] present an integrated thermo-economic optimisation method for different ORC architectures using various heat sources, working fluids and equipment types. Their work provides a good overview of cost estimation correlations presented in literature for all relevant cycle components of an ORC. Astolfi et al. [22] describe the techno-economic optimisation of geothermally powered binary ORC plants, using the electricity production cost as an indicator to determine the ideal plant configuration for different geothermal heat sources. Their study highlights the importance of economic aspects in design optimisation when compared to plant design procedures based only on thermodynamic optimisation. In contrast to the previously described work, the authors introduce their own cost correlations for several plant components based on experience and cooperation with equipment manufacturers. Usman et al. [23] present a techno-economic comparison of air-cooled and cooling tower based ORC systems for different geographical locations, taking into account the local climate constraints. The performance is evaluated based on the levelized cost of electricity and the specific capital investment per kW for the respective plants. Their cost estimation is based on the previously described method by Walraven et al. [24], who provide

a study on economic system optimisation for air-cooled geothermal ORCs. In a more general work, Lemmens [18] presents an overview of different cost engineering techniques and their application ORC systems. The work provides cost estimation data for ORC plants over a wide range of power capacities and compares multiple cost estimation approaches against the known cost of an existing ORC plant. Among the observed cost estimation methods, the module costing technique delivers the most reliable results, according to the author.

The combination of the aforementioned processes in an RHP has been proposed for different applications, ranging from the use in net-zero energy buildings [25] over the use as a sector-coupling technology [26] to the use in PTES systems [27]. Currently, most attention is given to RHPs in the context of PTES systems, where Frate et al. [28] and Dumont et al. [29] present a good overview of the recent research activities in this field. Kosmadakis and Panagiotis [30] evaluate the potential and cost-effectiveness of an RHP in an industrial waste heat recovery context using specific plant cost values reported in literature. Garcia-Saez et al. [31] perform an energetic and economic evaluation of a solar ORC-CHP plant, using parts of the plant reversibly as an HTHP with a separate compressor and expander unit. In a previous study, the authors of this work investigated the application of an RHP in a geothermal combined heat and power plant (CHP), looking at the economic viability of the whole geothermal project [32]. While the findings indicate a minor benefit of an RHP compared to a geothermal CHP with only an ORC, the previous conference paper from 2022 does not examine the RHP's suitability for peak load coverage, especially in comparison to other conventional peak load technologies. Moreover, the previous work had several limitations, such as limited scalability of the applied compressor model, no consideration of the air-cooled condenser's (ACC) part load behaviour and no investigation towards the economically optimal ACC sizing.

In summary, the literature provides many detailed studies on stand-alone geothermal ORC and HTHP systems, including off-design and techno-economic evaluations, as well as several investigations of reversible heat pump (RHP) concepts in other contexts. However, comparable analyses of RHPs for geothermal applications are still missing. The following Table 1.1 summarises relevant publications and highlights that a detailed thermo-economic study of geothermal RHPs, as conducted in this work, addresses this research gap. It also highlights the importance of the condenser in geothermal power plants as one of the key components for an optimal design. Furthermore, combining the findings from the market reports on ORC [21] and HTHP [14] systems as well as the literature on RHP systems, such as Weitzer et al. [33], demonstrates the significant variations of the technological readiness level (TRL): While both ORC and HTHP systems have a TRL of 9, RHP are currently still in a range between 4 and 5, highlighting also the need for further studies regarding the potential upscaling and future economic implementation.

1.3. Contribution of this work

The previous literature review highlights, on the one hand, the promising potential of RHPs for geothermal applications. By being a significant novel advanced development compared to the already commercialised ORC and HTHP technology, it can improve the economic performance of geothermal district heating systems and contribute to the substitution of fossil peak boilers. On the other hand, a detailed thermodynamic and economic assessment considering the system design and detailed component part load behaviour is missing. Especially against the background of the growing interest in geothermal HTHP systems for peak-load coverage and their often challenging economic viability due to the low capacity factor, a better understanding of how RHPs can improve the economic performance of a geothermal project is of high relevance. Thus, this work provides the first in-depth techno-economic analysis of an RHP for peak load coverage in DHNs, comparing it to the most relevant alternative peak-load

Table 1.1
Overview of key publications on geothermal ORC, HTHP and RHP systems.

Reference	System type	Application context	Economic assessment	Off-design?	Limitation vs. this work
Astolfi et al. (2014) [34]	ORC	Geothermal power	LCOE optimisation	Partial	Sole power generation
Walraven et al. (2015) [24]	ORC	Air-cooled power plant	Thermo-economic optimisation	Yes	Sole power generation
Usman et al. (2017) [23]	ORC	Various climate zones and Air-cooler	Thermo-economic comparison	Yes	Sole power generation
Astolfi et al. (2020) [35]	ORC	Geothermal ORCs with hybrid condenser	Techno-economic evaluation	Partial	Sole power generation
Tammone et al. (2021) [36]	ORC	Partial-evaporated ORC	Techno-economic	Partial	Sole power generation
Galiati et al. (2024) [37]	ORC	Air condenser for geothermal ORC	Techno-economic performance	Partial	Component focus; sole power generation
Jeßberger et al. (2022) [7]	HTHP	Geothermal DHN	Techno-economic	Partial	Conference-level; no reversible mode
Jeßberger et al. (2024) [38]	HTHP	Geothermal DHN (peak load)	Annual techno-economic	Yes	No reversible mode; brine mass flow decreased during summer while HTHP operates
Ungar et al. (2024) [39]	HTHP	Deep closed loop systems	LCOH evaluation	No	no reversible mode; focus on CO ₂
Zuffi and Fiaschi (2025) [40]	HTHP	Assessment various geothermal scenarios in Africa	LCOH evaluation	No	No focus on DHN, no reversible mode
Quoilin et al. (2016) [41]	RHP	Building applications	–	Yes	no economic assessment; focus on small scale application
Kaufmann et al. (2022) [32]	RHP	Geothermal CHP	Yes	Simplified	Conference level; rather simplified modelling approach (conference paper)
Steger et al. (2022) [42]	RHP	Carnot batteries	–	Yes	No techno-economic assessment; no geothermal use case
Daniarta et al. (2023) [43]	RHP	Geothermal CHP	–	No	No thermo-economic assessment
Velanparambil Ravindran et al. (2023) [44]	RHP	Industrial waste heat recovery	–	Yes	No geothermal application; small scale system
This work	RHP	Geothermal DHN peak-load	Detailed thermo-economic	Yes	First detailed geothermal RHP peak-load study

technologies, i.e. regular HTHPs and gas boilers. To ensure realistic boundary conditions, a load profile derived from an existing GHP's operation data is used to determine the required plant capacity and evaluate the technical performance of the plant. This is done by annual cycle simulations of hourly resolution. For a first techno-economic comparison of the different technologies, the cycle simulations of HTHP and ORC mode only use simplifying assumptions for the heat exchangers, but a size-independent part load model for twin-screw machines. The latter allows accounting for realistic capacity limitations of the plant, which are often neglected for the sake of simplicity. Having a major influence on the power generation and the overall cost of an RHP, the ACC is then investigated in-depth by including a detailed ACC model in the simulations. To facilitate the higher computational cost of the ACC model, its part-load impact is assessed by using simplified load profiles according to the typical-day method proposed in the VDI 4655 guideline. Special focus is put on the optimal selection of reference profiles for each typical day using a genetic algorithm to achieve a good profile approximation with the typical-day method. This method is potentially very useful for a wider audience working with typical-day methods. Furthermore, a sensitivity analysis with respect to energy prices and ACC sizing is performed to account for the uncertainties in these factors.

In summary, this study extends the start-of-the-art by providing:

- a detailed techno-economic assessment of an RHP system for geothermal applications, considering realistic load profiles, part-load models and different ACC sizes
- an economic comparison of the RHP system to conventional peak load technologies for geothermal heating like HTHPs and gas boilers

- a sensitivity analysis that investigates the favourability of different peak-load technologies for geothermal heating under different economic boundary conditions

Therefore, the work provides valuable insights to both academia and industry regarding the most economically viable peak-load technology for geothermal heating plants. By providing in-depth insights into a detailed techno-economic modelling approach for geothermal RHP, considering also component design and off-design behaviour, the research community can build on the method of this work for further general and case-specific case studies. Furthermore, by studying the design and operation of a potential commercial RHP demonstrator at a real existing geothermal site, the industry also gets highly valuable insights on the expected component sizing and required investment costs to make the technology viable. Therefore, this work contributes to the further development of the currently not commercialised RHP technology, paving the way to a potential first worldwide industrial demonstrator for geothermal applications in the mid-term future.

2. Methods

Annual simulations with an hourly resolution are conducted to evaluate the technical performance of the RHP with respect to heat supply and electricity generation. For this purpose, the plant design of a GHP connected to an RHP and realistic load profiles are first introduced. The subsequent sections then describe the simulation methods used for the cycle and component simulations. Moreover, economic evaluation methods are introduced, including CAPEX and OPEX estimation alongside suitable economic performance indicators.

Fig. 2.1. HTHP operation mode (a) and ORC operation mode (b) of an RHP in a GHP.

2.1. Simulation methods

This section focuses on the simulation methods that are applied in this work. It starts with a description of the general plant design and provides the load profiles, which are derived from a real plant. Subsequently, a typical-day method is introduced that allows for reducing the number of simulation points while maintaining a realistic load profile. Finally, the procedures and assumptions for cycle- and component modelling are introduced.

2.1.1. Plant design and load profiles

The integration of an RHP into a GHP is depicted in Fig. 2.1. Sub Fig. 2.1(a) shows how the geothermal brine and the DHN are connected to the plant in HTHP operation. The whole brine stream is first used to supply heat to the DHN before it is passed on to the HTHP's evaporator, where it is further cooled down before reinjection to the reservoir. On the condenser side, the HTHP rejects heat to a fraction of the DHN stream at an elevated temperature level. For the sake of completeness, the fossil peak-load boiler and its integration into the GHP are also depicted. Depending on the plant capacity, the RHP might not be able to cover the whole peak load, and the boiler would have to cover the remaining heat load. However, following the goal of decarbonisation, a full peak load coverage by the HTHP is intended, and the HTHP should be sized accordingly. During times of low demand in the DHN, the plant operates in ORC mode as depicted in Fig. 2.1(b). In this case, only a part of the brine is used to supply heat to the DHN while the remaining brine is directed towards the ORC's evaporator in a parallel configuration, meaning that the excess heat for the ORC is available at wellhead temperature. Since cooling water is often not available, the ORC's condenser is an air-cooled condenser for this application. The boiler is also included in the ORC layout in Fig. 2.1(b) for the sake of completeness, but does not serve a purpose during ORC operation. Concluding, the major components required for the RHP are: An evaporator and a reversible twin-screw compressor (both used in both operation modes), a pump and an air-cooled condenser for the ORC mode, and finally, a throttle valve and a water-cooled condenser for the HTHP mode. In theory, other compressor types, such as scroll machines, could be used reversibly for expansion, but the requirements of a MW-scale plant confine the choice to twin-screw machines. Underlining the technical feasibility and satisfactory performance in both operational modes, the operation of reversible twin-screw compressors was recently investigated in experimental studies by the authors of this work [45] and Weitzer et al. [46].

The plant load profile and the deducted operation trajectory used in this work combine the heat demand profile of an existing geothermal heating plant south of Munich and hourly temperature data [47] for the location of Munich, both for the time period between April 2022 and March 2023. A maximum constant geothermal brine mass flow of

81.52 kg/s is obtained from the wellhead at a temperature of 106 °C, which represents a common temperature level for geothermal heating plants in southern Germany [48]. Fig. 2.2(a) shows the operational strategy of the DHN over the course of a year. While the return temperature of the DHN is mostly around 55 °C, the DHN flow rate and the supply temperature change significantly based on the heat demand. Hence, the operational conditions of the HTHP can vary widely with respect to temperature lift and condenser duty, requiring reliable part-load modelling for realistic performance calculation. Fig. 2.2(b) depicts the maximum available heat from the geothermal well, the real course of the DHN heat duty over the year and the load duration curve. To obtain the peak load operation, the hourly heat duty values from the DHN heat demand profile are sorted in a decreasing fashion. The real heat demand curve for the DHN indicates peak load operation during the winter months, mostly December, January and February.

From the intersection of the sorted demand curve and the well potential curve, 1267 peak load hours (requiring HTHP operation) and 7493 h of excess heat (enabling ORC operation) can be obtained. These numbers highlight the previously introduced problems (c.f. Section 1.1) of mono-functional HTHP or ORC plants. Specifically, the low number of potential operating hours for the HTHP leads to a low capacity factor, reducing its economic viability. In contrast, the large number of ORC operating hours during summer months with high ambient temperatures reduces the annual power output and thereby the economic performance of the ORC. The RHP system can potentially abate these problems by a significant increase in the plant's capacity factor as it operates during both of the above-indicated time slots throughout the year. Finally, the broad range of excess heat indicates significant fluctuations in heat source mass flows for the ORC, also requiring accurate part-load models in this operational mode.

Conventional GHPs mostly already include a fossil boiler, which is operated during maintenance times or operational failures of the geothermal well. This work is based on the assumption that the existing boiler can only cover the maximum duty of the geothermal well. Hence, either another smaller boiler or a suitably sized HTHP need to be installed to cover the peak load in times of insufficient supply from the well. This assumption is reasonable, as the GHP from which the operational data is obtained also features several separate boilers. Moreover, this scenario is realistic and highly relevant for GHPs that can currently cover the DHN heat demand from the geothermal well but face insufficient peak load coverage due to the current massive expansion of many DHNs, as for example reported for the existing networks in Grünwald and Unterhaching in Southern Germany [6]. Considering the peak load deduced from Fig. 2.2(b), the additional boiler or HTHP would need to cover a maximum heat duty of roughly 8.8 MW. From a practical perspective, a boiler will most likely be installed for redundancy purposes to cover times when the geothermal well is not operational (which would also restrain the HTHP from operation). For

Fig. 2.2. Operational states of the DHN (a) and heat duties in the DHN (a) over the course of a year.

the economic comparison, only the demand-related cost of the boiler will be considered, while also investment- and operation-related costs are considered for the RHP and the HTHP.

While the previously presented hourly load profiles enable a highly realistic plant evaluation, the calculation of several thousand operating points is associated with high computational effort, especially if numerically expensive component models are included. A method to maintain realistic load profiles while reducing the number of operational points is introduced by the typical-day approach described in the VDI 4655 guideline [49]. For the sake of brevity, a full description of the typical-day method and its application on the above load curves is discussed in Appendix A.1 of the appendix for the interested reader.

2.1.2. Cycle simulation

The simulation of both operation modes is conducted based on thermodynamic cycle models implemented and solved in MATLAB [50]. The RHP uses a reversible open-drive twin-screw compressor. The machine performance and part-load behaviour in compressor and expander modes are calculated using a scalable generalised compressor model previously developed by the authors [51], which is further discussed in Section 2.1.3. The model allows for the consideration of realistic capacity limitations associated with the maximum and minimum machine speeds. Since the RHP is highly flexible in its operating conditions, the heat exchangers have to be considered with extra care. This especially applies to the ACC, which can strongly limit the achievable condensation pressure and the maximum heat rejection rate in real applications. To limit the complexity, a two-step approach with respect to the heat exchangers is chosen. In the first step, the RHP's required capacity is estimated based on pinch-point assumptions for all heat exchangers. In the second step, the heat exchangers of the optimal plant capacity are sized, and the plant's technical performance is recalculated considering detailed part load behaviour for the ACC at different ACC sizes.

Each operational point of the plant, i.e. each hour of the load profile, poses an optimisation problem that is described separately for ORC and HTHP operation in the subsequent two paragraphs. In short, the net electric power output is optimised during ORC operation while the optimisation seeks to minimise the electrical power consumption during HTHP operation. The resulting numerical optimisation problem is constrained by several practical boundary conditions imposed by the load profiles and technical limitations of the system. The optimisation problem is solved by the use of a sequential quadratic programming algorithm that adapts selected process variables to find the constrained optimum for each load point.

During ORC operation, the mass flow rate of the working fluid is adjusted by the solving algorithm in order to maintain 10 K superheating at the expander entrance for the respective evaporating pressure, which is optimised to achieve the maximum net power output. While

droplet formation is no problem for twin-screw machines, sufficient superheating after the evaporator is required in real applications to ensure proper separation of lubricant and working fluid [52], which mostly happens in an oil separator placed between the evaporator and the expander. Especially for HCFO refrigerants such as R1233zd(E), which is used in this work, a high affinity between refrigerant and lubricating oil has been examined in experimental studies [45,52], indicating that lower superheating (e.g. 5 K) would adversely affect the separation of oil and working fluid after the evaporator. As stronger superheating requires a larger condenser for non-recuperated cycles (due to the mostly dry working fluids in ORCs), a value of 10 K is deemed suitable in this work. In real applications, this value is, of course, subject to optimisation. In the first simulation step, the ORC condensation pressure is set to satisfy the pinch point constraint in the condenser, assuming condensation to a saturated liquid. In contrast, it becomes a further degree of freedom in the second simulation step when the ACC's part load behaviour is accounted for.

The mass flow rate of the working fluid in HTHP mode is adjusted by the solving algorithm in order to cover the heat demand of the DHN. The oil separation is usually done after the compressor, and the requirements for evaporator outlet (or compressor inlet) superheating in HTHP mode are accordingly less strict and depend on the specific system design and refrigerant. For the sake of consistency, a value of 10 K is also used for the superheating in HTHP mode, representing a realistic value according to literature [9]. While the HTHP condensation pressure level is fixed by the pinch point requirement in the first simulation step, it becomes a degree of freedom in the second simulation step, where the pinch points in the plate heat exchangers (PHEX) are only constrained to a minimum value of 5 K. The evaporation pressure of the HTHP and the ORC is a solver parameter in both simulation steps and is only confined by a constraint that ensures an evaporator pinch point larger than 5 K.

The pinch point temperature differences of 5 K are common for large heat pumps [16] and ORC units [53] and should also yield reasonable HEX sizes in both operation modes. In both simulation steps, the cycle parameters are optimised to minimise the required compressor power or maximise the net power generation of the ORC. Table 2.1 summarises the most important simulation parameters of the plant for both operation modes. An efficiency value for the fossil boiler is given with the HTHP values, as the peak load coverage by a fossil boiler is the comparison scenario for HTHP peak load coverage. In both operation modes, the mass flow rates determined by the solver have to fulfil the constraint that the compressor or expander operates within a speed range of 500 to 4500 rpm to ensure realistic capacity limits.

The brine inlet temperature for HTHP operation is given as an approximate value since the actual values depend on the momentary operational state of the DHN (cf. Fig. 2.2(a)). Based on an average value from the investigated plant's operational data, a pinch point of

Table 2.1
Simulation parameters for ORC and HTHP mode of the RHP, including literature references where applicable.

ORC Operation			HTHP Operation		
Expander inlet superheating in K	10.00	[52]	Compressor inlet superheating in K	10.00	[9]
Evaporator pinch ΔT in K	>5.00	[53]	Evaporator pinch ΔT in K	>5.00	[16]
Condenser pinch ΔT in K	5.00	[53]	Condenser pinch ΔT in K	5.00	[16]
Isentropic pump efficiency	0.65	[54]	Brine inlet temperature in °C	~65	–
Electric motor/generator efficiency	0.95	[55]	DHN return temperature in °C	~55	–
Cooling air ΔT in K	10.00	–	Brine flowrate in kg/s	81.52	–
Brine inlet temperature in °C	106	–	Boiler efficiency in %	90	[56]

10 K is assumed for the cold end of the DHN/brine heat exchanger, leading to the brine inlet temperature of approximately 65 °C in Table 2.1. It is noted that the fixed condenser pinch point values given in Table 2.1 are only valid for the first step of the calculations. In the second simulation step, they are replaced by solver constraints, which ensure positive pinch points for the ACC and pinch points ≥ 5 K for the PHEXs. The brine flow rate in ORC mode and the DHN water flow rate heated by the HTHP are determined by the load profile presented in Section 2.1.1. In this context, the DHN fraction heated by the HTHP is arbitrarily increased whenever the original flow rate would require the HTHP to operate below its minimum load and hence be switched off. This follows the goal to maximise the amount of renewable heat supply and leads to a slightly decreased use of the geothermal heat for the respective load operational points. However, as the brine inlet temperature to the HTHP evaporator is increased in this case, a higher COP can be expected for the HTHP, reducing the impact of increased electricity demand by longer HTHP operation to a certain extent.

Several simulative studies investigate the choice of working fluid for RHP systems, especially for their application in PTES systems. Considering both natural refrigerants, such as hydrocarbons and synthetic refrigerants (including R1234ze(E), R1233zd(E), R1234yf and R245fa), most authors conclude that R1233zd(E) is the optimal working fluid for RHP systems. This is justified by a combination of high cycle efficiencies in both operating modes [13,27,57,58], low system pressures [13] and a high vapour density [59], with the latter two aspects positively affecting the system cost. In addition, its favourable safety properties (i.e. low flammability and toxicity) and low environmental impact ultimately make it preferable over natural refrigerants with similar thermodynamic performance according to the previously cited sources. For this reason, R1233zd(E) is also chosen as an appropriate working fluid within this work. To further underline this choice, it is important to note that all relevant experimental facilities that investigate RHP units also work with R1233zd(E) for the previously stated reasons [45, 46,60,61]. The thermo-physical properties for the cycle calculation in MATLAB are obtained from REFPROP [62].

2.1.3. Component modelling

This work considers the reversible twin-screw compressor and the ACC with special care since their physical behaviour imposes distinct limitations on real plants. In explicit, the speed limitations of the reversible compressor and the attached electrical machines have a major influence on the maximum working fluid flow rates in both operational modes of the RHP. Additionally, the area limitations of the ACC and the practical limitations of cooling air velocity can limit the heat duties transferred within the plant and hence need to be considered for realistic plant performance evaluation.

The reversible compressor is modelled using a generalised low-order model for twin-screw compressors recently developed by the authors [51]. The model yields the isentropic and volumetric efficiencies based on the suction flow rate and the applied pressure ratio, allowing the calculation of the compressor speed and required shaft power. It allows for realistic part-load modelling of twin-screw compressors independent of their size (with respect to the swept volume) and mostly independent of their built-in volume ratio. This feature makes the model especially useful for this study since different compressor capacities are considered in the plant sizing procedure. The low

computational cost of the model is another decisive factor, as extensive annual simulations with integrated optimisation are mostly not feasible with more detailed physical models. For an in-depth model description, the interested reader is referred to the original publication [51]. Similar to the approach for reversible twin-screw compressors proposed by Kosmadakis and Neofytou [63], the expander efficiencies are also calculated based on the previously described model. Only the swept volume, which is used in the model equations for the expander, is corrected by dividing the compressor's swept volume by its built-in volume ratio. To yield the best prediction accuracy from the low-order model, the built-in volume ratio of 3.1 used during model development [51] is also applied in this work. It is well matched to the pressure ratios observed in this work, also during ORC operation where pressure ratios are moderate due to the rather low heat source temperature (c.f. Section 3.2.2). It is important to note that twin-screw expanders usually show a significantly smaller efficiency decline for larger applied pressure ratios compared to twin-screw compressors. In this context, the chosen approach to model the twin-screw expander in this work likely underestimates its efficiency as it assumes the same dependency between applied pressure ratio and machine efficiency for both the compressor and expander. This falsely diminishes the ORC's power output in the present study, decreasing its technical and economic performance. While there is no easy way to abate this issue, it should be kept in mind for the later interpretation of the RHP's techno-economic performance.

After the compressor sizing in the first step, the required heat exchangers, i.e. PHEXs and a finned-pipe air-cooled condenser, are sized based on detailed physical models. For the PHEXs, a finite volume model adapted from the one proposed by Braimakis and Karellas [17] is used. To account for the working fluid R1233zd(E), the heat transfer correlation proposed by Zhang et al. [64] is used for the condenser, while the correlation of Lee et al. [65] yields the respective values for the evaporator. The finite volume model used in the sizing procedure exhibits a high computational cost as it requires a numerical solver, strongly diminishing its applicability in extensive simulations. For this reason, the PHEXs, i.e. the HTHP's evaporator and condenser and the ORC's evaporator, are again modelled based on energy balances and a minimum pinch point of 5 K in the second simulation step. This simplification can be justified by two arguments. Firstly, the PHEXs are sized with a pinch point of 5 K for the maximum-duty load point, which would effectively result in smaller pinches for almost all other operational points when real heat exchanger behaviour is accounted for. For the HTHP operation, the pinch point assumption hence results in slightly higher pressure ratios and, accordingly, lower COPs, yielding a rather conservative plant performance estimation compared to real heat exchanger behaviour. This also applies to ORC operation, where the pinch point assumption effectively reduces the ORC power generation by reducing the maximum feasible evaporation pressure. Secondly, the performance of RHP and HTHP is afflicted in the same fashion, not favouring one technology in the subsequent economic evaluation.

As described in Section 2.1.2, the part-load behaviour of the ACC is only considered in the second simulation step. The required heat exchange area of the ACC is determined from the results of the first simulation step, using a detailed physical ACC model proposed by Irrgang et al. [66]. While this model still requires a numerical solver, its computational cost is significantly lower compared to the physical

model of the PHEXs, making it more suitable for integration in the cycle simulation. Some of the model features (i.e. the air face velocity and fan power consumption) need to be considered as constraints and optimisation variables in the overarching ORC simulation in the second simulation step. While it is directly yielded from the ACC model by Irrgang et al. [66] in the second simulation step, the ACC's electricity consumption is calculated according to Lazzaretto et al. [67] as $P_{el,ACC}$ [kW] = $0.15 \cdot \dot{m}_{air}$ [kg/s] in the first simulation step. A brief graphical description of the ACC design with relevant geometrical parameters is provided in Fig. A.2 in the appendix. The respective parameter values used in this work are presented in Table A.2 in the appendix. A detailed model description extends the scope of this work, and the interested reader is hence referred to the original publication by Irrgang et al. [66].

The ORC's working fluid pump is only considered with a fixed isentropic efficiency of 65% (c.f. Table 2.1), which should be a realistic value for large-scale pumps [54].

The last major component to consider is the geothermal brine pump submerged in the well. Looking at Fig. 2.2(b), it becomes apparent that the maximum amount of brine is not required throughout the whole year to cover the DHN heat demand in a conventional GHP. Hence, the brine pump can be operated in part load, especially during the summer months, to reduce its electricity consumption and thereby reduce the plant's overall operational expenditures. As the ORC operation requires additional brine, which would not necessarily be pumped in a conventional GHP, additional pumping cost is caused by the ORC operation. To ensure a fair economic evaluation, the additional required pumping power and the associated cost need to be accounted for. Usually, brine pumps are only capable of limited part load and plant operators oftentimes hesitate to conduct frequent and strong load changes [68] in order to extend the pump's life span (with the pump being a major cost factor for GHPs [69]). The operational data from the plant, which the load profile of this work is based on, shows a minimum brine flow rate of approximately 53 kg/s even for very low heat demands during the summer months. Hence, this value (corresponding to a minimum brine pump part load of 63% with respect to mass flow) is used as the lower part load limit for the brine pump in this work. During ORC operation, only brine mass flow rates exceeding this value are considered to cause additional costs. In his dissertation, Schlagermann provides a method to estimate the electricity consumption of brine pumps based on reported efficiencies in different GHP and geothermal CHP projects [70]. For the sake of brevity and readability, the detailed calculation methodology is provided in Appendix A.5 in the appendix.

2.2. Economic evaluation methods

In this section, the economic evaluation methods of this work are introduced. This includes estimation methods for the initial investment cost but also calculation routines for operational cost and revenue streams. Finally, the aforementioned cost constituents are combined in Section 2.2.3, which introduces the levelised cost of heat as a performance metric based on an annuity method.

2.2.1. Investment cost calculation

In order to cover all the required components of the observed plant design, cost estimation methods of different authors are taken into account in this work. The method proposed by Kosmadakis et al. [16] for an HTHP is used wherever possible since it was published rather recently, enables cost estimation for semi-hermetic twin-screw compressors and covers most of the components required in the plant. As described in Section 2.1.3 this work uses a model developed with an open-drive twin-screw compressor. However, the behaviour of a semi-hermetic machine can be considered very similar. The only implication is that no separate motor needs to be considered for the cost estimation

Table 2.2

Purchased ACC cost for a total condenser surface area of 53,527 m² according to different cost correlations from literature (scaled to 2024 value).

Correlation	ACC cost in €
Walraven et al. [24]	2,183,664
Turton et al. [72]	5,931,032
Lecompte et al. [73]	1,028,470

using the method of Kosmadakis et al. [16]. The cost estimation is based on an exponential scaling law method of the form

$$C_i = C_{i,ref} \cdot \left(\frac{X_i}{X_{i,ref}} \right)^y \quad (1)$$

where C_i is the component cost of the component i with the cost-relevant property value X_i . The constant parameters $C_{i,ref}$, $X_{i,ref}$ and y are the reference cost, the reference property value and the scaling exponent for the considered component type, respectively. Similar scaling laws are proposed by other authors [17,22,24] whose cost estimation methods, however, partly yield significantly different results. Hence, this work tries to stick to the method and the parameters given by Kosmadakis et al. [16] for most of the components to obtain a consistent cost estimation. The reference parameters and exponents for Eq. (1), together with the reference year and the original source, are summarised in Table A.3 in the appendix.

Following the approach of Braimakis and Karellas [17] the required working fluid receiver volume is calculated as the sum of the evaporator and condenser volumes on the working fluid side multiplied by a factor of 1.2.

The cost-relevant property for the twin-screw compressor in Table A.3 is the conveyed suction volumetric flow rate. As this property is dependent on the machine speed, there is no clear indication of what flow rate to use here. Hence, a compressor suction flow rate $\dot{V}_{comp,ref}$ at a reference speed n_{ref} of 50 Hz (being the design speed of many rotating equipment) is used to ensure a fair cost estimation for different compressor sizes (in terms of swept volume V_s). The compressor suction flow rate is calculated according to Eq. (2), neglecting internal leakages for the sake of simplicity.

$$\dot{V}_{comp,ref} = V_s \cdot n_{ref} \quad (2)$$

For ACCs, there is comparably little literature on detailed models suitable for sizing, and also, the published cost estimation methods differ vastly. The ACC model by Irrgang et al. [66], which is used in this work, is developed from a similar ACC model proposed by Langiu et al. [71] and yields detailed geometrical data suitable for cost evaluation. The cost estimation method for the ACC used in this work was proposed for geothermal ORC applications by Walraven et al. [24] and hence fits the scope of this work well. It relates the cost of the ACC to its bare-pipe surface area. To give a perspective on the deviations between different cost estimation methods for the ACC, Table 2.2 briefly compares the cost obtained from different correlations from literature for a total condenser surface area of 53,527 m² (corresponding to 2446 m² of bare-pipe area), which is the ACC surface area according to the initial sizing (c.f. Section 3.2.1).

The cost values for the components summarised in Table A.3 are valid for the reference year given in the table and need to be adapted to the price level of 2024 using the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CEPCI). The component cost $C_{i,2024}$ for the year 2024 is accordingly calculated by Eq. (3). The relevant values of the CEPCI are summarised in Table A.4 in the appendix.

$$C_{i,2024} = C_{i,ref} \cdot \frac{CEPCI_{2024}}{CEPCI_{ref}} \quad (3)$$

Following the method of Kosmadakis et al. [16], the cost for piping and tanks $C_{p,t}$ of the plant is calculated as ten percent of the preliminary

equipment cost according to Eq. (4).

$$C_{p-t} = 0.1 \cdot (C_{\text{HEX}} + C_{\text{comp}} + C_{\text{receiver}} + C_{\text{pump}}) \quad (4)$$

Here, C_{HEX} includes the cost for the evaporator, the HTHP condenser and the ACC (including its fan and motor). The same approach is also taken to calculate the piping cost associated with the gas-fired boiler.

To obtain the total project cost, explicitly the overnight EPC (engineering, procurement and construction) investment cost, the cost engineering method used by Walraven et al. [24] for geothermal ORC plants is followed. The total project cost can be calculated as

$$C_{\text{project}} = \sum_i (f_{M,i} \cdot f_{P,i} \cdot f_{T,i} + f_1) \cdot C_{\text{equipment},i} \quad (5)$$

where i is iterated over all plant components including the working fluid and piping, using correction factors for non-standard materials ($f_{M,i}$), pressures ($f_{P,i}$) and temperatures ($f_{T,i}$). The installation cost factor f_1 is 0.6 and accounts for costs related to the erection, instrumentation and control (including electrical equipment) of the plant. Walraven et al. [24] propose a pressure correction factor of 1.5 for any equipment subject to pressures larger than 7 bar and a temperature correction factor of 1.6 for temperatures above 100 °C. Finally, they propose a material correction factor of 1.7 for any component made from stainless steel due to an increased risk of corrosion (concerning mainly the HEXs in contact with hot water). The respective correction factors for all components can be found in Table A.5 in the appendix.

2.2.2. Operational cost and revenue calculation

Besides the invested cost, previously discussed in Section 2.2.1, several cost and revenue streams associated with the operation of the plant are relevant for the techno-economic analysis. The operational cost for the GHP is based on different contributors. Firstly, there is the annual electricity cost of the working fluid pumps $C_{\text{el,pump}}$ and the ACC fans $C_{\text{el,fan}}$ in ORC mode next to the annual electricity cost for the compressors $C_{\text{el,comp}}$ in HTHP mode. When the boiler is used for peak load coverage, there is the annual spending on natural gas C_{fuel} to fuel the peak-load boiler.

The annual electricity cost $C_{\text{el},i}$ of the component i (i.e. pump or compressor) can be calculated by Eq. (6)

$$C_{\text{el},i} = \left[\sum_j (P_{\text{shaft},i,j} \cdot t_j) / \eta_{\text{el}} \right] \cdot c_{\text{el}}, \quad (6)$$

considering the mechanical shaft power $P_{\text{shaft},i,j}$ of the respective component i , the electrical efficiency of its drive η_{el} (provided in Table 2.1) and the electricity purchase cost c_{el} . The variable t_j is the operation time in the load point j within the respective plant operation mode throughout the year. The ACC's electricity consumption is either directly estimated based on the Lazzaraetto [67] correlation given in Section 2.1.3 or calculated from the physical model, using an isentropic fan efficiency of 63% and an electrical efficiency of 90% for the attached motor as proposed in the original publication [66].

A similar approach is chosen in Eq. (8) to calculate the annual fuel-related cost. To also consider the cost of the associated CO_2 from the gas boiler, Bauer et al. [74] introduce the so-called clean fuel price $c_{\text{fuel, clean}}$, which is calculated from the fuel purchase price c_{fuel} , the emission factor of the respective fuel EF_{fuel} and the cost for European emission allowances (EUA) c_{EUA} as follows:

$$c_{\text{fuel, clean}} = c_{\text{fuel}} + EF_{\text{fuel}} \cdot c_{\text{EUA}}. \quad (7)$$

From this cost, the total fuel-related operating cost C_{fuel} are obtained from Eq. (8) in which $\dot{Q}_{\text{boiler},j}$ is the peak-load heat duty supplied to the DHN by the fossil boiler and η_{boiler} is the boiler efficiency (provided in Table 2.1).

$$C_{\text{fuel}} = \left[\sum_j (\dot{Q}_{\text{boiler},j} \cdot t_j) / \eta_{\text{boiler}} \right] \cdot c_{\text{fuel, clean}} \quad (8)$$

The annual revenue R_{el} of the RHP stems from the sale of electricity during ORC operation. It is calculated based on Eq. (9).

$$R_{\text{el}} = \left[\sum_j (P_{\text{shaft,exp},j} \cdot t_j) \cdot \eta_{\text{el}} \right] \cdot c_{\text{el}} \quad (9)$$

In this equation, $P_{\text{shaft,exp},j}$ is the expander shaft power for the operation hour j throughout the year.

As more recent values are not yet published, German electricity prices for the first half of 2024 are used. Industrial purchase prices of 232.8 €/MWh for electricity [75] and 67.8 €/MWh for natural gas [76] are used. For emission-related cost, an emission factor of 0.202 t CO_2 /MWh for natural gas [74] and an EUA price of 70 €/t CO_2 (valid for late 2024 [77]) are used. Further, this study assumes that the feed-in tariffs for electricity are equal to the purchase prices. This aims to avoid biased calculations based on potential short-term feed-in tariffs and is discussed in more detail in the sensitivity analysis in Section 3.2.3.

2.2.3. Levelised cost of heat

As the main purpose of this study is the investigation of different peak-load technologies for GHPs, the most relevant economic indicator in this the $LCOH$ for the respective peak-load coverage. The $LCOH$ can generally be calculated based on Eq. (10)

$$LCOH = \frac{A_N}{Q_{\text{peak}}} \quad (10)$$

where A_N is the total annuity of the respective peak load coverage facility and Q_{peak} is the cumulative annual peak-load heat demand. In this study, the annuities of the RHP, the HTHP and the gas boiler are calculated according to the method proposed in the VDI guideline 2067 [78] with some simplifications which are subsequently discussed. Generally, the total annuity is defined as in Eq. (11)

$$A_N = A_{N,C} + A_{N,D} + A_{N,O} - A_{N,R} \quad (11)$$

where $A_{N,C}$, $A_{N,D}$ and $A_{N,O}$ are the capital-related, demand-related and operation-related annuities, respectively. The total annuity is reduced by revenues from electricity sales in this study, which is reflected by the last term $A_{N,R}$ in Eq. (11). For the sake of brevity and readability, the detailed calculation of the individual annuity constituents and associated assumptions are discussed in Appendix A.4.

3. Results

This chapter starts with a discussion of the required plant sizing with respect to heat pump capacity and the respective plant performance from the initial simulation step. Subsequently, a detailed techno-economic analysis of the plant is conducted, considering the impact of part load modelling for the ACC and different ACC sizes. This analysis uses the optimal typical-day reference load profile determined in Appendix A.1 in the appendix. Finally, the chapter finishes with a detailed sensitivity analysis regarding different energy prices.

3.1. Initial plant sizing

With the overarching goal to completely replace fossil-based technologies, the optimal plant sizing needs to be able to cover the full peak demand of the DHN. This is achieved by sizing the HTHP's compressor adequately. The compressor needs to be large enough to enable full peak demand coverage while avoiding over-dimensioning and, hence, unnecessarily high plant costs. To determine the optimal compressor size, the compressor's swept volume is varied between 0.0525 m³ and 0.0975 m³ in 30 steps for the load point with the highest thermal DHN load during peak load operation. This is done using the simulation configuration described in Section 2.1.2, where minimum pinch points of 5 K are assumed for the heat exchangers, while the compressor's part-load behaviour and capacity limits are realistically

Fig. 3.1. Required boiler duty for peak load coverage at the maximum DHN load operating point with different swept compressor volumes (a) and heat demand coverage by the optimally sized heat pump (b).

portrayed by the scalable polynomial model. The optimal compressor size is reached at the minimum swept volume that does not require additional heat supply by a fossil boiler. This is depicted in Fig. 3.1(a), which shows the remaining required boiler duty for different swept volumes. The smallest swept volume that does not require additional firing is determined to be 0.078 m^3 . This value is used for all further simulations to ensure a sufficient heat pump capacity during peak load times.

Fig. 3.1(b) shows the respective demand coverage of the optimally sized heat pump with the previously determined swept volume for the load duration curve of the DHN. It is visible that the heat pump can fully cover the demand during the complete peak load time. It can further be observed that the maximum duty of the HTHP (which is obtained at maximum compressor speed with the selected swept volume) accounts for 8.8 MW, which aligns with the maximum peak load heat demand identified from the DHN load profile in Section 2.1.1 (also c.f. Fig. 2.2(b)). On the right side of Fig. 3.1(b), the minimum compressor speed (i.e. 500 rpm) and its effect on the heat pump's minimum load can be observed. When the minimum speed is reached, the condenser duty cannot be reduced any further, leading to an oversupply of heat to the DHN. In this case, the heat pump is operated at minimum load, and the amount of heat transferred to the DHN from the geothermal brine is reduced by changing the split ratio of the DHN mass flow between the brine-DHN heat exchanger and heat pump condenser (c.f. Fig. 2.1). This, for once, avoids boiler operation for small peak loads and, moreover, enhances the heat pump's COP by raising the heat source temperature for the heat pump.

The ORC gross electrical power generation is depicted in Fig. 3.2(a) depending on the available brine mass flow and the ambient temperatures. A continuous rise of the maximum power output can be observed with rising brine mass flows. During summer and transition times, when larger brine mass flows are available, the ambient temperature has a major impact on gross power generation, especially for geothermal ORC systems with a rather low temperature of $106 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in this case study. Higher ambient temperatures lead to a drastic decrease in power generation by increasing the condensation pressure and consequently decreasing the power output of the expander.

The spread in gross power generation is less pronounced for smaller brine mass flows, as these coincide with winter days and colder transition days that do not show larger temperature swings over the day. The strong influence of the ambient temperature on the gross power generation leads to partially negative net electric power generation of the ORC as depicted in Fig. 3.2(b). In the operating hours with negative net power generation, the generator's power generation is not sufficient to compensate for the electricity consumption of the

working fluid pump, the ACC and the brine pump. Next to the ambient temperature, which has a direct impact on the ORC's thermal efficiency by limiting its achievable pressure ratio, the brine mass flow also has a notable influence. Lower brine mass flows enable a lower brine outlet temperature within the ORC's feasible operational range, reducing exergy destruction in the evaporator and thereby facilitating higher thermal efficiencies. Overall, net electric thermal efficiencies between 4.45% and 7.35% are obtained at the given heat source temperature of $106 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. These values align well with the net electric thermal efficiencies that were recently obtained by the authors on a small-scale RHP test rig for similar operating conditions. In explicit, net thermal efficiencies around 3-5% were obtained experimentally for a heat source temperature of $110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [45]. It is important to note that the experimental investigation at that heat source temperature was conducted at significantly higher condensation pressures compared to the simulations, reducing the power output and thermal efficiency in the process.

In addition, it needs to be considered that small-scale facilities are generally less efficient and that the technology will certainly gain in efficiency during further development towards large-scale plants, making the simulated values realistic.

A distinct kink in the curvature of the maximum net power generation can be observed in Fig. 3.2(b). This can be attributed to the minimum brine pump load of 53 kg/s . As described in Section 2.1.3, all values for the total brine mass flow below 53 kg/s are not considered to cause additional electricity consumption, as the pump needs to be operated for the DHN anyway. As a result, the brine pump's electricity consumption for ORC operation shows an approximately linear increase until a brine mass flow of roughly 30.5 kg/s (being the difference of maximum and minimum total brine mass flow from the well) for the ORC is reached. Afterwards, the value stays constant as the additional brine mass flow is covered by the minimum total brine mass flow of 53 kg/s , resulting in a different curve for the net electricity generation. In a real application, operating points with negative net power generation are not realised, and the ORC would not be operated under these conditions. Hence, these points are not accounted for in the subsequent evaluation of the plant performance. Of the 7101 valid operating hours for the ORC (with a brine mass flow available for the ORC larger than 5 kg/s), 6270 h yield a positive net power generation. During this time, the ORC generates a gross electricity amount of 3588.7 MWh. Considering the annual demands of the working fluid pump, the ACC and the brine pump of 90.1 MWh, 647.5 MWh and 2008.2 MWh, respectively, a net electricity amount of 842.9 MWh is yielded. These numbers highlight the massive impact of the brine pump consumption once more. In contrast, the HTHP provides a total heat amount of 3102.3 MWh throughout the year while

Fig. 3.2. ORC gross electrical power output (a) and net electrical power output (b) depending on the available geothermal brine mass flow and ambient temperatures.

consuming 713.2 MWh of electrical energy. The HTHP operation yields a weighted COP of 4.4. In this context, the weighted COP is obtained by multiplying the COP of each operating hour from the load profile by its respective condenser heat duty and dividing the sum of those terms by the total annual provided heat duty.

3.2. Techno-economic evaluation

This section provides the techno-economic plant evaluation that is based on the previously described technical plant performance. It starts by discussing a first economic evaluation that is based on the technical performance with pinch-point assumptions and the full hourly load profile, which helps to understand the influence of the different load profile types discussed in Appendix A.1 in the appendix. Then, the influence of the ACC's size and part-load performance is discussed in detail before the section concludes with a sensitivity analysis for the most relevant impact factors.

3.2.1. Economic evaluation with pinch-point assumptions

The economic evaluation is first conducted based on the simulation of the full hourly load profile with pinch-point assumptions to give an initial perspective on the economic performance of the proposed plant concept. The same evaluation is subsequently conducted based on the typical-day load profile to derive the implications of the typical-day method on economic performance. To evaluate the economic performance of the considered plant and compare it to alternative peak load technologies, a cost analysis must be made. For this purpose, all major plant components are sized using the methods and physical models introduced in Section 2.1.3. All PHEXs are sized to handle the maximum appearing heat duty with a pinch point of 5 K. The ACC is sized to satisfy the requirements of the maximum duty operating point (with respect to heat duty and condensing pressure) at an air face velocity of 3 m/s, which is often recommended by plant operators as an upper limit due to noise emissions. For the working fluid pump, the maximum volumetric suction flow rate is considered for cost estimation. The determined component sizes (based on each component's characteristic size property) are summarised in Table A.6 in the appendix. The respective purchased component costs for the RHP and a correspondingly sized peak load boiler are presented in Table 3.1 together with their respective share of the total equipment cost. In order to validate the applied cost estimation methods and add a further peak load coverage method for reference, Table 3.1 also provides the aforementioned values for a regular HTHP, removing all ORC components from the cost estimation.

At the bottom of Table 3.1, the total equipment cost and the total project cost are provided together with the specific investment cost in

€/kW for each peak load technology, with the latter being calculated from the total project cost and the maximum heat duty of the peak load system. This allows further validation of the cost estimation methods by comparing the specific cost to published values from literature and real projects. It can be observed that the boiler exhibits the lowest specific cost at 143 €/kW_{th}, while the respective costs for the HTHP and RHP are much higher at 369 €/kW_{th} and 835 €/kW_{th}. For HTHPs in a comparable size range and with comparable sink temperatures, specific costs between 200 €/kW_{th} and 700 €/kW_{th} are reported for existing projects in literature [79].

Compared to these values, the cost estimation for the HTHP provided in Table 3.1 seems reasonable. The cost estimation for the RHP, however, seems very high. Here, the ACC's cost is an order of magnitude larger compared to the remaining components and accounts for roughly 57 % of the purchased equipment cost. Literature sources on common cost shares for the ACC differ vastly and range from values of 16 % [18] to a staggering amount of 80 % [24].

To further validate the cost estimation methods, the ORC's purchased equipment costs and total project cost are calculated by eliminating the heat pump-specific components from the RHP section of Table 3.1. This results in purchased equipment cost of 3,570,116 € and total ORC-specific project cost of 6,643,316 €, yielding specific costs of 3593 €/kW_{el} and 6687 €/kW_{el} based on purchased equipment cost and project cost, respectively. In this calculation, the ACC accounts for roughly 61 % of the purchased equipment cost. Literature reports specific costs of 1000–2000 €/kW_{el} or 2000–4000 €/kW_{el} for geothermal ORC projects based on purchased module cost or project cost, respectively [18]. These numbers indicate that the cost estimation for the ORC is significantly too large. One possible explanation is the significant oversizing of the ACC when it is dimensioned for the maximum-duty load point. While this sizing might be optimal from a technical perspective, the economically optimal sizing can differ significantly, as described by Astolfi et al. [22]. This further motivates to examine the impact of the ACC's size and part load behaviour on the techno-economic plant performance, which is done in detail in Section 3.2.2.

For the cost calculation according to Table 3.1 and the technical performance data of the plant, the annuities for each peak load technology are calculated according to the method described in Section 2.2. Fig. 3.3(a) shows the constituents to the total annuities for each peak load technology in Table 3.1 based on the hourly load profile. Naturally, the RHP shows the highest capital- and operation-related annuities, as these values directly correlate to the total project cost provided in Table 3.1. The demand-related annuity is significantly smaller than the capital-related annuity for the RHP, and the negative annuity from the electricity sales revenues completely compensates for it. For the

Table 3.1
Calculated costs for different peak load technologies based on plant evaluation with pinch point assumptions.

	RHP		HTHP		Boiler	
	Cost in €	Share in %	Cost in €	Share in %	Cost in €	Share in %
Evaporator	240,003	6.30	240,003	18.17	–	–
HP condenser	216,748	5.69	216,748	16.41	–	–
ACC	2,183,664	57.34	–	–	–	–
Pump	34,165	0.90	–	–	–	–
Compressor	655,106	17.20	655,106	49.60	–	–
ACC fan and motor	43,681	1.15	–	–	–	–
Receiver	14,872	0.39	14,872	1.13	–	–
Working fluid	74,070	1.94	74,070	5.61	–	–
Piping and tanks	346,231	9.09	120,080	9.09	61,034	9.09
Boiler	–	–	–	–	610,342	90.91
Total equipment cost in €		3,808,539		1,320,878		671,377
Project cost in €		7,371,588		3,256,048		1,262,188
Spec. cost in €/kW _{th}		835		369		143

Fig. 3.3. Annuities of different peak load technologies with pinch point assumptions for the hourly load profile (a) $LCOH$ comparison for plant sizing based on the hourly and the typical-day load profiles (b).

HTHP, the capital-related annuity also has the largest share in the total annuities, but its share of the total annuities is less dominant compared to the RHP. The demand-related annuity is slightly smaller, and the operation-related annuity only accounts for roughly a fifth of the total annuities. For the boiler, in contrast, the demand-related annuity dominates the total annuities with a share of roughly 75%. These numbers imply that the economic viability of the RHP concept should be more resilient towards changing electricity prices, while the economic viability of the HTHP and the boiler strongly depend on the respective electricity and gas prices. This is examined in more detail in Section 3.2.3.

In order to validate the use of the typical-day approach (in addition to Appendix A.1 in the appendix), Fig. 3.3(b) provides the $LCOH$ values yielded from plant sizing based on the hourly and the typical-day load profiles. For this comparison, the correction factor of 0.67 for the annual net electricity generation (derived in Appendix A.1) is already applied to the typical-day results. It can be observed that the respective $LCOH$ values for all considered technologies show little to no deviation, regardless of the used load profile. Since the hourly heat demand profile is quite well-matched, the typical-day method yields similar costs for all heat pump components, leading to a very minor deviation in the HTHP's $LCOH$. For the Boiler, only demand-related annuities are considered for the $LCOH$ calculation, and as the provided heat cancels out when combining Eqs. (8) and (10), the same value is yielded for both profiles. The RHP's $LCOH$ is somewhat higher for the typical-day profile due to differences in the load points used for component sizing. This leads to reduced ACC cost for the typical-day profile, which is sufficient to have a relevant impact on the $LCOH$. However, this inaccuracy introduced by the typical-day method does

not change the qualitative or quantitative results in a relevant fashion, and the overall economic viability of the different technologies remains unchanged.

The respective $LCOH$ values depicted in Fig. 3.3(b) for the RHP, the HTHP and the boiler are: 196.4€/MWh, 157.3€/MWh and 99.9€/MWh using the hourly profile and 180.5€/MWh, 150.4€/MWh and 99.9€/MWh with the typical-day load profile. To give a perspective on how each individual annuity constituent depicted in Fig. 3.3(a) contributes to the overall $LCOH$ for the three compared technologies, Table 3.2 provides the respective contributions of each annuity constituent. The total $LCOH$ and the capital- and operation-related $LCOH$ constituents for the boiler are given in brackets for the sake of completeness. However, as discussed in Section 2.1.1, only the demand-related annuities are considered for the economic comparison. To analyse the impact of both operational modes on the $LCOH$, the demand-related and revenue-related $LCOH$ constituents from Table 3.2 need to be investigated for HTHP and ORC operation, respectively. To account for the fact that the revenue-related annuity decreases the total annuity according to Eq. (11), the revenue-related $LCOH$ constituent is given as a negative value in Table 3.2.

These numbers indicate that the boiler is by far the most economically viable peak-load technology with the electricity and gas prices of 2024 provided in Section 2.2.2. With the above-presented sizing and cost structure, the RHP is not competitive with the other peak load technologies. However, the question of whether this changes with a smaller ACC and fluctuating energy prices remains to be answered. Consequently, the subsequent sections introduce a method that allows for proper judgment of the impact of different ACC sizes and conduct a sensitivity analysis based on the economically ideal ACC size.

Table 3.2

Contributions of the annuity constituents to the overall $LCOH$ for the different peak-load technologies for the full hourly load profile.

Technology	Total $LCOH$ in €/MWh	$LCOH_{N,C}$ in €/MWh	$LCOH_{N,O}$ in €/MWh	$LCOH_{N,D}$ in €/MWh	$LCOH_{N,R}$ in €/MWh
RHP	196.4	135.8	72.4	65.3	77.1
HTHP	157.3	60.0	32.0	65.3	–
Boiler	(127.9)	(17.1)	(10.9)	99.9	–

Fig. 3.4. Gross (a) and net (b) electric power generation of the ORC with and without consideration of the ACC part load model at the initial ACC size according to Table A.6.

3.2.2. Influence of ACC part-load and sizing

In a first step, the impact of the ACC's part load behaviour is assessed by comparing the techno-economic plant performance of the RHP with the initial ACC sizing according to Section 3.2.1 (see also Table A.6). Fig. 3.4(a) shows the gross electric power generation of all valid operating points using the typical-day profile, while Fig. 3.4(b) depicts the corresponding net electric power generation of the ORC, both with and without consideration of ACC part load model. Before the differences are discussed, it is important to note that without the ACC model, the gross electricity generation was maximised during the optimisation as the ACC's electricity consumption was only accounted for by the Lazzaretto [67] correlation given in Section 2.1.3. In contrast, the net electricity generation is optimised when the physical model is used since it allows for a much more detailed calculation of the load-dependent electricity consumption in the ACC.

Without the ACC model, the gross electricity generation is slightly or significantly higher for operational points with higher available brine mass flow for the ORC, while it is fairly similar at lower brine mass flow rates. In contrast, the net electricity generation is rather similar for higher brine mass flow rates, while the values with consideration of the ACC model significantly exceed the values without an ACC model at lower brine flow rates. These differences can be explained by multiple factors. However, the investigation of the underlying technical phenomena is complex and would distract from the main focus of this work, which is the techno-economic comparison of different peak load technologies. For this reason, a detailed technical analysis regarding the impact of the ACC model is provided in Appendix A.6 in the appendix for the interested reader.

When comparing the scaled annual net electricity generation according to the typical-day profile without and with the ACC model, an increase from 840.1 MWh to 942.2 MWh can be observed. Despite the significant difference, this has only a minor impact on the economic viability of the RHP, decreasing its $LCOH$ from 180.5 €/MWh to 178.4 €/MWh, due to the dominating impact of the ACC cost for the initial ACC sizing. The previous discussion, and especially the detailed technical analysis of the ACC's part-load behaviour in Appendix A.6, show that considering a reliable part-load model for the ACC can have

a significant impact on the overall techno-economic performance of the RHP. It is, therefore, of key importance to consider the ACC model within the subsequent analysis of the optimal ACC size. As it was already pointed out in Section 3.2.1, the high specific cost of the ORC module indicates an initial over-dimensioning of the ACC. The annual simulations (using the typical-day profile and the ACC model) were hence repeated with ACC sizes corresponding to 75 %, 50 % and 25 % of its initial size (with respect to the ACC's face area). In this context, it is important to consider that the ACC size is a degree of freedom during the design process. While the RHP capacity is determined by the requirement to completely fulfil the local heat demand and substitute the fossil peak boilers, the sizing of the power plant is not determined by the local demand characteristic, since excess electricity can also be sold to the grid.

Table 3.3 summarises the most important techno-economic performance metrics for the different ACC sizes. As expected, the scaled annual net electricity generation decreases with smaller ACC sizes. However, the decrease in generated electricity is underproportional to the reduction of the ACC size, while the ACC cost's decline correlates more directly with its reduction in size. This leads to an economic optimum at 50 % of the initial ACC size, which exhibits the lowest $LCOH$ at a value of 145.4 €/MWh. Very similar $LCOH$ values for ACC dimensions of 50 % and 25 % of the initial ACC size can be observed. While the reduction in ACC cost is less pronounced for 50 % of the initial size, the annual net electricity generation is still relatively high (i.e. exceeding the annual compressor electricity consumption) and generates revenues, lowering the effective total annuity. For 25 % of the initial ACC size, in contrast, the annual net electricity generation shows a much sharper decline and is not sufficient to compensate for the compressor's annual electricity consumption. However, the much lower ACC cost compensates for the missing revenues and finally yields similar $LCOH$ values for 50 % and 25 %. Consequently, the smallest two ACC sizes enhance the RHP's economic viability past the HTHP with the energy prices of 2024 provided in Section 2.2.2.

To explain the disproportionate decline of the net electricity generation with decreasing ACC size, selected process parameters of the ORC need to be evaluated. Again, the required detailed analysis would

Table 3.3
Techno-economic plant performance of the RHP with different ACC sizes.

Size Fraction in % of initial	Scaled $E_{el,net,ORC}$ in MWh	ACC cost in €	spec. ORC cost in €/kWh _{el}	$LCOH$ in €/MWh _{th}
100	942.2	2,183,664	7591.4	178.4
75	924.0	1,690,403	6680.3	158.6
50	820.7	1,178,336	5759.4	145.4
25	513.7	635,847	5069.2	148.8

not promote readability at this point. The respective explanation is therefore also provided in [Appendix A.6](#) for the interested reader.

To give a perspective on the cost estimation's reliability, [Table 3.3](#) also provides the project-specific cost for the respective ORC system with the different ACC sizes. It can be observed that smaller ACCs push the specific cost closer to the range reported in literature while still remaining significantly higher. This again supports the suspicion that the literature correlations for ACC costs yield unrealistically high values. This was also confirmed by confidential talks with plant manufacturers, which report significantly smaller specific costs for ACC modules. However, as the provided numbers are confidential, this line of reasoning is not further pursued. Ultimately, smaller ACC costs would further boost the economic viability of the RHP system.

3.2.3. Sensitivity analysis

Since both gas and electricity prices have been subject to strong fluctuations within recent years, the question arises of how this impacts the economic viability of the previously discussed peak load technologies. Moreover, a large uncertainty is introduced for real applications by the ratio of electricity sales and purchase prices, defined as the electricity price ratio $r_{el-price} = c_{el,sales}/c_{el,purchase}$ in this work. Usually, purchase prices are considerably higher as they include, for example, taxes and grid fees. During recent years, the average ratio of electricity sales prices (i.e. day-ahead stock market prices) and purchase prices, calculated based on semi-annual average values for both, has shown massive fluctuations, making any specific value a random choice. For this reason, the impact of this ratio is examined later on in this section for some specific values. To cover all the above-mentioned aspects, multiple sensitivity analyses with respect to gas and electricity prices are conducted.

The first one is using the optimal ACC size identified in the previous section for the reference RHP system. [Fig. 3.5](#) shows the $LCOH$ for varying gas and electricity prices for the RHP and the HTHP in the form of contour plots. [Fig. 3.6\(a\)](#) depicts the analogous plot for the boiler. Due to the fact that the annual net electricity generation in ORC mode is larger than the compressor's annual consumption in HTHP mode (i.e. 694.1 MWh), the $LCOH$ of the RHP shows a linear decline with rising electricity prices since the electricity sales revenues increase. $LCOH$ values between 151.7 €/MWh and 142.2 €/MWh are observed for electricity prices between 100 €/MWh and 300 €/MWh. Naturally, no dependency on the gas price is observed. This narrow range of $LCOH$ for a rather wide range of electricity prices indicates a strong resilience of the RHP technology towards fluctuating energy prices and can hence help to de-risk the investment. However, as discussed in the previous section, careful initial sizing of the ACC is essential to yield competitive $LCOH$ values.

The behaviour of the HTHP's $LCOH$ value shows an inverted trend, with a linear decrease of the $LCOH$ for declining electricity prices. Also here, no dependency on the gas prices is observed. With a $LCOH$ range of 114.7 €/MWh to 167.1 €/MWh for electricity prices between 100 €/MWh and 300 €/MWh, the dependency on the electricity price is much more pronounced compared to the RHP. While significantly lower electricity prices (compared to currently seen prices) would make the HTHP more competitive with the gas boiler (with current gas prices), higher prices have a strongly detrimental effect and make it considerably less viable compared to the RHP system.

As expected, the boiler's $LCOH$ shows no dependency on the electricity price but a strong and linear increase of the $LCOH$ for increasing

gas prices. For gas prices between 20 €/MWh and 160 €/MWh the respective $LCOH$ rises from 41.6 €/MWh to 212.4 €/MWh. While low gas prices make the boiler by far the most attractive option for peak load coverage, higher prices push its viability way beyond the RHP and HTHP systems. It is important to note that the gas price refers to the purchase price and does not consider changes in the cost of European CO₂ emission allowances. With regard to the emission reduction goals of the European Union, the EUA prices will most likely see a significant rise in the coming years, which would push the $LCOH$ values for the boiler in [Fig. 3.6\(a\)](#) towards higher values. With this perspective, the future economic viability of the boiler is questionable.

To give a compact overview of the most competitive peak load technology for different energy prices, [Fig. 3.6\(b\)](#) shows a favourability map that indicates the most viable peak load technology for each combination of electricity and gas prices. In this context, the most favourable technology is the one that exhibits the lowest $LCOH$ for the specific combination of gas and electricity prices. It is important to note that this map is only valid for the specific plant sizing analysed in this work and with the assumption that the electricity sales price matches the purchase price (i.e. with an $r_{el-price} = 1$). The latter assumption is addressed later on. To add some perspective on the likely development of energy prices, the respective gas and electricity price combinations (based on semi-annual average values) between 2019 and 2024 [[75,76](#)] are added to the map. Since the second half of 2019, there has been a clear trend of rising gas and electricity prices (for various reasons which exceed the scope of this work) that move towards the RHP becoming the best option for peak load coverage. The current situation, with the gas boiler as the cheapest option for peak load coverage, could also be changed significantly by subsidies for large-scale heat pump systems, which are currently set in place by legislators.

Considering the very likely overestimation of the ACC cost, which is supported by the unrealistically high specific ORC cost and confidential information from manufacturers, the domain where the RHP is the most favourable system should, in reality, be larger than depicted in [Fig. 3.6\(b\)](#). This effect is showcased in [Fig. 3.7\(a\)](#), which depicts a favourability map for the optimised ACC size but with a 50 % cost reduction for the ACC. According to manufacturers, this value is realistic and can be backed up by the fact that ACCs are highly modular pieces of equipment, which are produced in large numbers and hence benefit from economy-of-scale effects, limiting the applicability of traditional cost estimation techniques. Moreover, a cost reduction by 50 % would also be achieved by applying the third ACC cost correlation provided in [Table 2.2](#), indicating that this cost reduction would be supported by published cost estimation methods from the scientific literature. This once more highlights the drastic impact of the uncertainties introduced by different cost estimation methods and calls for a further investigation of different cost correlations in future studies. It becomes clear that a reduced ACC cost can considerably shift the domain boundaries for the most favourable peak load technology, confining the HTHP domain to only very low electricity prices. However, due to the scarcity of publicly available pricing data for ACC, this result is mostly of a qualitative nature.

As stated at the beginning of this section, the electricity price ratio can considerably change the economic viability of the RHP. With lower price ratios, the revenue generated from electricity sales becomes increasingly less effective in reducing the overall annuity of the RHP. For this reason, it is beneficial to decrease the RHP's overall project cost by

Fig. 3.5. LCOH of the RHP (a) and the HTHP (b) for various gas and electricity prices.

Fig. 3.6. LCOH of the boiler for various gas and electricity prices (a) and favourability map of the different peak load technologies for an optimised ACC size (b) with selected historic half-year average energy prices [75,76].

Fig. 3.7. Favourability map of the different peak load technologies for a 50% reduction in ACC cost (a) and surplus LCOH of the RHP for different electricity price ratios with the smallest ACC (b).

using a smaller ACC. To show the effect of different realistic price ratios that have occurred in recent years (i.e. 0.3, 0.65 and 1.0), a sensitivity analysis based on the plant performance with the smallest considered ACC size (being 25% of the initial size) is conducted. This leads to a significant reduction in ACC cost (c.f. Table 3.3) but also reduces the ORC's annual net electricity generation to 513.7MWh, which is below the annual electricity consumption in HTHP mode (694.1 MWh).

Hence, the LCOH of the RHP now exhibits the same inverted dependency on electricity prices as the HTHP shown in Fig. 3.5(b), but still with smaller LCOH-spreads for the considered electricity price range.

Fig. 3.8 shows the respective favourability maps for electricity price ratios of 1.0 and 0.65. For a value of 0.3, the favourability map is identical to the one for a value of 0.65 in Fig. 3.8(b) and, therefore, not shown additionally. The results indicate that the RHP system is

Fig. 3.8. Favourability map of the different peak load technologies with the smallest ACC for electricity price ratios of 1.0 (a) and 0.65 (b) including selected historic half-year average energy prices [75,76].

only competitive for larger electricity price ratios, while smaller values favour boiler or HTHP systems exclusively. As Fig. 3.8(b) allows no conclusion on how much better the HTHP performs compared to the RHP system for smaller electricity price ratios, Fig. 3.7(b) shows the surplus $LCOH$ of the RHP for different electricity prices.

For small electricity price ratios (i.e. the value 0.3), the surplus $LCOH$ of the RHP is quite large, most likely making it noncompetitive, regardless of potentially lower ACC cost. However, for electricity price ratios of 0.65 and 1.0, the surplus $LCOH$ is rather small for a considerable range of electricity prices, and lower ACC cost could realistically enhance the RHP's favourability. Especially at project sites, where the GHP is integrated into other facilities with high energy demand (e.g. industrial sites), the effective electricity price ratio can be increased by using the ORC's electricity generation to cover on-site demand. In these cases, the RHP system would be an attractive option for renewable heat supply with a low risk towards fluctuating electricity prices.

4. Conclusion

This work presents a detailed techno-economic analysis, investigating the use of RHPs for peak load coverage in geothermal heating plants by means of annual plant simulations. The technical plant performance is first evaluated based on a realistic hourly load profile, which is derived from real operational data of a geothermal heating plant. The results are used to size the required plant components and conduct an economic analysis, comparing the RHP to conventional peak load technologies such as HTHPs and gas boilers. The results from this evaluation show that the gas boiler yields significantly lower $LCOH$ values (99.9€/MWh) than the HTHP (157.3€/MWh) and the RHP (196.4€/MWh) when the analysis is based on energy prices from the year 2024.

The results further indicate that the ACC size has a major impact on the RHP's economic viability and should be investigated in greater detail. For this reason, a detailed physical model is introduced to account for the part load behaviour of the ACC, which is used for heat rejection when the RHP is operated as an ORC. This allows to consider part load effects and investigate the impact of different ACC sizes on the overall economic plant performance. To keep the computational effort within reasonable boundaries when the ACC model is included in the cycle simulations, a reduced load profile is derived by applying the typical-day method according to the VDI guideline 4655. The simulation results obtained with the ACC model indicate that a more detailed modelling of the ACC has a significant impact on the technical plant performance, especially regarding the ACC's electricity consumption. Furthermore, the results show that the initially high $LCOH$ of the RHP is caused by

an over-dimensioned ACC and the ACC size can be reduced by 50% of its initial value without relevant reductions in annual net electricity generation. With a reduced ACC size, the RHP becomes much more competitive (yielding an $LCOH$ of 145.4€/MWh) and replaces the HTHP as the second-best peak load system after the gas boiler for 2024 energy prices.

To investigate the impact of fluctuating energy prices, different ACC sizes and varying electricity price ratios (i.e. the ratio of sales and purchase price), a detailed sensitivity analysis is conducted. It features favourability maps for different gas and electricity prices, compactly depicting the peak load technology with the lowest $LCOH$ for various ACC sizes and electricity price ratios. The results show that the boiler is mostly the cheapest option for peak load coverage when energy prices of recent years are considered. However, a rising effective gas price, which is likely considering decarbonisation goals, is strongly detrimental to the boiler's economic viability. The HTHP is often the best option for higher gas prices and always provides the cheapest option for peak load coverage when electricity prices are also low. However, the RHP often becomes the best option when high gas prices come along with higher electricity prices, as the RHP's $LCOH$ shows a much higher resilience towards fluctuating electricity prices. This attribute can be utilised to lower the investment risk when a renewable peak load system is required. While high electricity price ratios (e.g. achieved by on-site electricity demand coverage) are favourable for the RHP's economic viability, lower values render an RHP mostly non-competitive. Finally, the cost estimation methods from the literature yield unrealistically high ACC costs according to confidential talks with manufacturers and project developers. Lower ACC costs significantly boost the RHP's economic performance, which likely makes the RHP competitive for a large domain of electricity and gas prices. In general, the large deviations between different cost estimation correlations from literature introduce significant uncertainty in the economic analysis, calling for a comparison of different cost estimation correlations in future studies.

Thus, in summary, this work provides a detailed insight into the potential techno-economic performance of RHP systems for a real use case in the greater Munich area with a brine temperature of 106 °C. It shows that RHPs could play a beneficial role in future heating plants subject to uncertain energy prices. The presented methodology provides a valuable foundation for future case studies and general parameter variations. Such studies are required to enhance the understanding of the RHP's performance when varying boundary conditions come into play. This addresses the optimal sizing of the ACC in an overall optimisation routine for more scenarios regarding different brine temperatures, district heating demand profiles and supply temperatures. Furthermore, an attempt should be made to obtain more realistic ACC

price data from manufacturers in order to ensure a fair comparison to regular HTHPs for peak load coverage. This will further sharpen the picture of the potential commercial deployment of RHP systems as a novel geothermal surface technology, boosting the decarbonisation of the heating sector.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Florian Kaufmann: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hartmut Spliethoff:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Christopher Schifflachner:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Florian Kaufmann reports financial support was provided by Bavarian State Ministry of Education, Science and the Arts. Florian Kaufmann reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A

A.1. Typical-day clustering method

The typical-day approach described in the VDI 4655 guideline [49] introduces ten typical days that occur with a certain frequency throughout the year, depending on the geographical location or climate zone. Since each typical day is represented by a reference load profile (RLP) with an hourly resolution, a total of 240 system states must be calculated in the simulation.

In order to create the RLP for each typical day, this work combines daily and hourly weather data (e.g. ambient temperatures and cloudiness) for the location of Munich with the heat demand profile described in Section 2.1.1, all for the previously introduced time period of April 2022 to March 2023. The criteria for the typical-day categories (described by a three-letter code, see Table A.1) are daily mean cloudiness and daily mean temperature. The first letter of the category is either 'S' for summer, 'W' for winter, or 'T' for transitional. The criteria for each named season are a daily mean temperature greater than 15 °C, less than 5 °C, or a value in between, respectively. The second letter is either "W" for working days (including Saturdays) or "S" for Sundays. The third letter refers to cloudiness and is "B" for bright days with an average cloudiness less than 5/8 or "C" for cloudy days with an average cloudiness greater than or equal to 5/8. For summer days, cloudiness has little effect on the daily temperature curve, so it is neglected, and the third letter is simply "X". The frequency of each typical day obtained from the weather data is given in Table A.1.

There are different approaches when selecting suitable RLPs of all relevant process parameters for each typical day. A first approach starts by creating a mean 24-hour profile of either the ambient temperature or

the DHN heat demand over all days within each typical-day category. Using the mean profile, the root mean square error (RMSE) of the respective parameter's 24-hour profile is calculated for all days within each category, and the profile with the smallest RMSE is set as the RLP for the respective parameter of each category. The remaining 24-hour process parameter profiles (i.e. DHN temperatures, mass flows and ambient temperatures) for each typical day are then obtained from the same time slots of the detailed load profile that contains the respective RLPs. However, this approach can yield significant deviations in the load duration curve, leading to an underestimation of the peak load. For this reason, a second approach is proposed in this work: The ideal DHN heat demand RLP in each typical-day category is determined by a genetic algorithm solver, which minimises the deviation between the real sorted DHN heat demand profile and the sorted DHN heat demand profile yielded from the typical-day approach.

The three different approaches to selecting the RLPs are compared based on Fig. A.1. Fig. A.1(a) shows the sorted DHN heat demand curves derived from the original hourly profile and the different typical-day reference profiles obtained according to the methods described above. It is clear that the typical-day profiles based on mean temperature profile deviation and mean heat load profile deviation ("TD temp". and "TD heat" in Fig. A.1) underestimate the DHN heat demand during peak load hours. This results in a lower maximum heat duty during heat pump operation and overall lower annual heat generation from the heat pump due to fewer operational hours of the heat pump. Also, during times of excess heat, i.e. the operational domain of the ORC, the DHN heat demand profile is approximated rather poorly by the two previously mentioned approaches.

The approach, which identifies the ideal reference profiles using a genetic algorithm ("TD opt". in Fig. A.1), approximates the load duration curve much better, leading to a similar number of HP operating hours as the original hourly load profile.

Fig. A.1(b) compares some key energy metrics based on annual plant simulations using the original load profile (c.f. Section 3.2.1) and the different typical-day reference profiles. As mentioned before, the total annual amount of heat provided to the DHN by the heat pump is best matched by the optimised reference profiles. The same can be observed for the total annual electricity consumption of the compressor, which is nearly identical to the value yielded from the original profile. During ORC operation, all typical-day reference profiles overestimate the annual net electricity generation, but the optimised profile shows the smallest deviation again. Here, the hourly profile yields only 67 % of the annual net electricity generation predicted from the typical-day method with the optimised RLPs. Since the load duration curve (and hence the brine mass flow for the ORC) is rather well matched by the optimised reference profiles, the deviation in electricity generation most likely stems from significant deviations between the reference temperature profile and the actual ambient temperatures in the original load profile. Since the reference profiles obtained by optimisation with a genetic algorithm yield the lowest deviations from the original load profile results, they are used for investigating the impact of the ACC's size and part load behaviour in Section 3.2.2. It is clear that the significantly increased electricity generation with the typical-day profile would unrealistically favour the economic viability of the RHP compared to the HTHP. The annual net electricity generation yielded from the typical-day profile is therefore reduced by a correction factor of 0.67 to enable a fair technology comparison.

A.2. ACC design and modelling parameters

See Fig. A.2 and Table A.2.

A.3. Cost estimation parameters

See Tables A.3–A.6.

Table A.1
Frequency of typical days according to VDI 4566 between April 2022 and March 2023 in Munich.

Category	SWX	SSX	WWB	WWC	WSB	WSC	TWB	TWC	TSB	TSC
Category No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Frequency	94	16	10	75	1	18	16	118	0	17

Fig. A.1. Load duration curves (a) and annual heat and electricity generation from the RHP (b) for different typical-day reference profile identification methods.

Fig. A.2. ACC design used in this work adapted from Irrgang et al. [66].

Table A.2
ACC geometry parameters (according to Fig. A.2) used in this work.

Parameter	Value
Tube rows n_{rows}	6
Tube passes n_{tp}	2
Tube length L_t in m	15
Outer tube diameter d_o in mm	31.75
Inner tube diameter d_i in mm	28.25
Tube distance L_p in mm	69.85
Tube thermal conductivity (steel) k_t in $W m^{-1} K^{-1}$	45
Fin diameter d_f in mm	63.5
Fin thickness t_f in mm	0.3
Fin distancing L_f in mm	2.31
Fin thermal conductivity (aluminium) k_t in $W m^{-1} K^{-1}$	237

A.4. Annuity calculation methods

The capital-related annuity is calculated from the initial project cost (as described in Eq. (5)) and the annuity factor a according to Eq. (12).

$$A_{N,C} = C_{project} \cdot a \tag{12}$$

The annuity factor is, in turn, depending on the observation period τ and the interest factor q and can be obtained from Eq. (13).

$$a = \frac{q - 1}{1 - q^{-\tau}} \tag{13}$$

The demand-related annuity is calculated according to Eq. (14)

$$A_{N,D} = A_{D,1} \cdot a \cdot b_D \tag{14}$$

where $A_{D,1}$ is the demand-related annuity in the first year of operation and b_D is the price dynamic cash value factor for demand-related costs. While $A_{D,1}$ needs to be replaced by the annual electricity consumption cost of all components (i.e. ACC, compressor and pumps, c.f. Eq. (6)) for the RHP, it is replaced by the annual fuel consumption cost for the system with a boiler.

It is expected that no additional staff is required in the GHP for the operation of the peak-load facilities. Hence the operation-related annuity only depends on the maintenance-related annuity in the first year of operation $A_{M,1}$ and the respective price dynamic cash value

Table A.3
Cost estimation correlation parameters for Eq. (1).

Component i	$C_{i,ref}$	$X_{i,ref}$	y	Ref. year	Source
Plate heat exchanger	15,526 €	42 m ²	0.8	2013	[15]
Semi-hermetic screw compressor	19,850 €	279.8 m ³ /h	0.73	2013	[15]
Working fluid receiver	1,444 €	0.089 m ³	0.63	2013	[15]
Working fluid pump	80,004 €	0.7 m ³ /s	0.441	2016	[17]
Air-cooled condenser	167,000 €	200 m ²	0.76	2013	[24]
AC Fan + Motor	13,100 €	50 kW	0.76	2013	[24]
Gas-fired boiler	256 €	1 kW	0.745	1982	[80]

Table A.4
Chemical engineering plant cost index (CEPCI) for selected years.
Source: [81].

Year	1982	2013	2016	07/2024
CEPCI	315.0	567.3	541.7	798.8

Table A.5
Correction factors for EPC cost calculation.

	RHP			Boiler		
	$f_{M,i}$	$f_{P,i}$	$f_{T,i}$	$f_{M,i}$	$f_{P,i}$	$f_{T,i}$
Evaporator	1.7	1.5	1.6	–	–	–
HP condenser	1.7	1.5	1.0	–	–	–
ACC	1.0	1.0	1.0	–	–	–
Pump	1.0	1.5	1.0	–	–	–
Compressor	1.0	1.0	1.0	–	–	–
ACC fan and motor	1.0	1.0	1.0	–	–	–
Receiver	1.0	1.5	1.0	–	–	–
Piping and tanks	1.0	1.5	1.0	1.7	1.5	1.6
Boiler	–	–	–	1.0	1.0	1.0

Table A.6
Design-point component sizes used in Eq. (1) for cost estimation.

Component	Size parameter	Size parameter value
Evaporator	A_{plate} in m ²	839.3
HTHP Condenser	A_{plate} in m ²	738.9
Semi-hermetic screw compressor	$\dot{V}_{suction}$ in m ³ /h	21,060
Working fluid receiver	V in m ³	2.095
Working fluid pump	\dot{V} in m ³ /s	0.0421
Air-cooled condenser	$A_{bare-pipe}$ in m ²	2,442.6
ACC Fan + Motor	$P_{el,fan}$ in kW	155.4
Gas-fired boiler	Q in kW	9,807.0

factor for maintenance b_M , as described by Eq. (15).

$$A_{N,O} = A_{M,1} \cdot a \cdot b_M \quad (15)$$

The maintenance-related annuity is obtained from Eq. (16)

$$A_{M,1} = C_{project} \cdot \left(\frac{f_{repair} + f_{s+i}}{100} \right) \quad (16)$$

using plant-dependent factors for continuous repairs f_{repair} and servicing and inspection f_{s+i} .

The revenue-related annuity depends on the annuity factor, the price dynamic cash value factor for revenues b_R and the revenues from electricity sales in the first year of operation $R_{el,1}$, which is reflected in Eq. (17).

$$A_{N,R} = R_{el,1} \cdot a \cdot b_R \quad (17)$$

Finally, the respective price dynamic cash value factors are calculated according to Eq. (18)

$$b = \frac{1 - \left(\frac{r}{q}\right)^\tau}{q - r} \quad (18)$$

depending on the price change factor r , which is assumed to be equal for all considered types of costs and revenues. The interest factor and the price change factor strongly depend on global macroeconomic

and geopolitical developments. They are, hence, inherently difficult to predict and sometimes subject to strong fluctuations. To reduce the impact of recent spikes caused by a global pandemic and geopolitical tensions, an inflation-based price change factor of 1.0213 and an interest factor of 1.0131 are used in this work. These values are based on an average inflation of 2.13% [82] in the Eurozone and a weighted average European Central Bank interest rate of 1.31% [83] between 2003 and 2023. Furthermore, an observation period of 20 years is set. The VDI guideline 2067 provides f_{repair} and f_{s+i} values of 1 and 1.5 for heat pumps or 1 and 2 for gas boilers, respectively [78].

A.5. Brine pump modelling

The required electric power $P_{el,BP}$ of the brine pump can be calculated according to Eq. (19).

$$P_{el,BP} = \frac{P_{hyd}}{\eta_{mech,BP} \cdot \eta_{el-mech,drive}} \quad (19)$$

In this work, a mechanical pump efficiency $\eta_{mech,BP}$ of 0.7 and an electro-mechanical efficiency $\eta_{el-mech,drive}$ of 0.86 for the attached drive are assumed in accordance with Schlagermann [70]. The hydraulic pumping power P_{hyd} is determined based on the volumetric brine flow rate \dot{V}_{brine} , the brine pump's pressure head H_{BP} , the brine density ρ_{brine} and the gravitational acceleration g according to Eq. (20).

$$P_{hyd} = \rho_{brine} \cdot g \cdot \dot{V}_{brine} \cdot H_{BP} \quad (20)$$

The pump's pressure head is strongly dependent on the geological circumstances and the technical execution of the respective production well. Therefore, it needs to be calculated for each production well individually. In this work, the pump's head is determined from Eq. (21), which considers the installation depth of the brine pump H_{inst} , the pressures at the pump's inlet $p_{in,BP}$ and outlet $p_{out,BP}$ and finally the pressure loss in the production well above the pump Δp_{loss} .

$$H_{BP} = H_{inst} + \left(\frac{p_{out,BP} - p_{in,BP}}{\rho_{brine} \cdot g} \right) + \frac{\Delta p_{loss}}{\rho_{brine} \cdot g} \quad (21)$$

Assuming a constant piping diameter at the pump's in- and outlet, the contribution of the fluid velocity is neglected in Eq. (21). The pressure loss in the production well is calculated based on the current flow rate using the Darcy-Weisbach-equation (c.f. Eq. (22)) assuming a cylindrical borehole pipe with a constant diameter d_{BP} and a friction factor λ obtained from the Moody-diagram based on the roughness e .

$$\Delta p_{loss} = \lambda(e) \cdot \frac{8 \cdot \rho_{brine} \cdot H_{inst}}{\pi^2 \cdot d_{BP}^5} \cdot \dot{V}_{brine}^2 \quad (22)$$

All relevant parameters for Eqs. (19) to (22) are summarised in Table A.7.

A.6. ACC part-load performance

This section investigates the underlying technical phenomena explaining the differences in gross and net electricity generation with and without the ACC model introduced in Section 3.2.2. It further explains the reasons for the disproportionate decline in net electricity generation with declining ACC size shown in Table 3.3.

Fig. A.3. working fluid mass flows (a) and pressure levels (b) of the ORC with and without consideration of the ACC part load model at the initial ACC size according to Table A.6.

Fig. A.4. ACC electricity consumption at initial ACC size according to Table A.6 (a) and with 50% lower ACC size (b).

Table A.7
Parameters for brine pump power calculation.

Parameter	Value	Unit	Source
$\eta_{\text{mech,BP}}$	0.7	–	[70]
$\eta_{\text{el-mech,drive}}$	0.86	–	[70]
g	9.81	kg/(m s ²)	–
ρ_{brine}	988	kg/(m ³)	–
H_{geo}	700	m	plant operator
$p_{\text{out,BP}}$	20	bar	plant operator
$p_{\text{in,BP}}$	15	bar	plant operator
d_{BP}	0.225	m	plant operator
e	0.00025	m	assumption (steel pipe)

The differences in gross and net electricity generation with and without the ACC model shown in Fig. 3.4 can be explained by considering several effects. Firstly, as shown in Fig. A.3(a), the working fluid mass flow is significantly higher for higher brine mass flow rates when no ACC model is considered. While the condensation pressure remains fairly similar with and without the ACC model, the evaporation pressure is mostly significantly higher with the ACC model for higher brine mass flows (c.f. Fig. A.3(b)). This is possible as the lower working fluid mass flow of these points is associated with a smaller cooling of the heat source, and the evaporation pressure can consequently be increased without violating the minimum pinch point temperature difference (which mostly occurs at the transition from preheating to evaporation).

However, there is no consistent trend in the overall expander pressure ratios, and the higher gross electricity generation without the ACC model can mainly be attributed to the higher working fluid mass flow rates. Still, the question remains why the net electricity generation does not behave concurrently with the gross electricity generation. This difference is caused by massive differences in the ACC’s electricity consumption as depicted in Fig. A.4(a). When the Lazzaretto correlation is applied without the ACC model, the ACC’s electricity consumption is massively overestimated, often by a factor of 2-3. The physical ACC model correlates the fan’s electricity consumption to the momentary air velocity and the corresponding air side pressure drop in the ACC. It can, hence, be considered much more accurate compared to the Lazzaretto correlation. Before discarding the Lazzaretto correlation as inaccurate, it is necessary to assess the ACC size impact on its prediction accuracy.

For this reason, the ACC’s electricity consumption, according to the Lazzaretto correlation and the ACC model, are compared for the plant simulation with a 50% smaller ACC in Fig. A.4(b).

It can be observed that both methods predict more similar electricity consumption with a smaller ACC size, at least for a significant share of operational points. This can be accounted to the higher average air velocity (and accordingly a higher pressure drop), which is required to yield a similar power generation from a smaller ACC.

The disproportionate decline in net electricity generation with declining ACC size shown in Table 3.3 can be explained by several interdependent effects. Firstly, Fig. A.5(a) shows the gross electric power generation with the initial and the (economically) optimal ACC size, being 50% of the initial size. It can be observed that the gross

Fig. A.5. Gross (a) and net (b) electric power generation of the ORC with initial (100%) and optimal (50%) ACC size.

Fig. A.6. Face air velocity (a) and electricity consumption (b) of the ACC with initial (100%) and optimal (50%) ACC size.

electric power does not significantly deviate for most operation points, which is caused by mostly very similar working fluid mass flow rates and pressure levels in the evaporator and condenser. However, the same gross power output also means that comparable amounts of heat need to be rejected via the ACC.

Considering the significantly smaller heat exchange area of the condenser at optimal ACC size, this requires a drastically increased air velocity, which is confirmed by the ACC's face air velocity for both ACC sizes depicted in Fig. A.6(a). The increased air velocity comes along with an increased electricity consumption of the ACC fans for the smaller ACC, which is depicted in Fig. A.6(b).

The higher electricity consumption of the ACC ultimately yields slightly lower net electric power generation for 50% of the initial ACC size (c.f. Fig. A.5(b)) at comparable gross powers. With further decreasing ACC sizes, the upper limit for the face air velocity of 3 m/s is soon reached, which results in a reduction of the achievable gross (and net) electricity generation. This explains the more pronounced reduction in net electricity generation for the smallest ACC size in Table 3.3 and the respective very minor further decline of *LCOH* for the smallest ACC.

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2025.120484>.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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